

1 **Title: Efficacy of CDK4/6 inhibitors in preclinical models of malignant**
2 **pleural mesothelioma.**

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57 **Abstract**

58 **Background:** There is no effective therapy for patients with malignant
59 pleural mesothelioma (MPM) who progressed to platinum-based chemotherapy
60 and immunotherapy.

61 **Methods:** We aimed to investigate the antitumor activity of CDK4/6 inhibitors
62 using *in vitro* and *in vivo* preclinical models of MPM.

63 **Results:** Based on publicly available transcriptomic data of MPM, patients with
64 *CDK4* or *CDK6* overexpression had shorter overall survival. Treatment with
65 abemaciclib or palbociclib at 100 nM significantly decreased cell proliferation in
66 all cell models. Both CDK4/6 inhibitors significantly induced G1 cell cycle arrest
67 thereby increasing cell senescence and increased the expression of interferon
68 signalling pathway and tumour antigen presentation process in culture models of
69 MPM. *In vivo* preclinical studies showed that palbociclib significantly reduced
70 tumour growth and prolonged overall survival using distinct xenograft models of
71 MPM implanted in athymic mice.

72 **Conclusions:** Treatment of MPM with CDK4/6 inhibitors decreased cell
73 proliferation, mainly by promoting cell cycle arrest at G1 and by induction of cell
74 senescence. Our preclinical studies provide evidence for evaluating CDK4/6
75 inhibitors in the clinic for the treatment of MPM.

76 **Keywords:** malignant pleural mesothelioma, CDK4/6 inhibitors, drug therapy,
77 MPM *in vivo* models.

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83 **Introduction**

84 Malignant pleural mesothelioma (MPM) is an aggressive, locally invasive and
85 currently not curable malignancy of the pleura, which is associated with
86 occupational and para-occupational exposure to asbestos (1). Although asbestos
87 use is banned in many countries, asbestos-insulated buildings are present
88 throughout the world and some countries are still manufacturing and using large
89 quantities of asbestos (2). Germline mutations in *BAP1* and in other cancer
90 susceptibility genes such as *PALB2*, *BRCA2*, *CHEK2* and *MLH1* have been
91 identified in about 10-15% of patients with MPM (3-7).

92 Treatment options are limited for patients with advanced MPM (8). Cisplatin plus
93 pemetrexed has been the standard treatment in patients with advanced MPM (9).
94 The addition of bevacizumab to chemotherapy modestly improved overall
95 survival, but this treatment is not available in all countries (10). Single agent
96 immunotherapy has demonstrated limited efficacy in the relapsed setting versus
97 chemotherapy in the PROMISE trial, while in the CONFIRM trial nivolumab has
98 been superior to placebo (11, 12). Recently, in the CheckMate-743 study, dual
99 immune checkpoint inhibition with nivolumab plus ipilimumab has demonstrated
100 superiority to platinum plus pemetrexed in the 1st line setting and has been
101 already approved by the FDA (13).

102 Comprehensive genomic analysis of MPM revealed that is dominated by
103 inactivation of tumour suppressor genes by multiple mechanisms including single
104 nucleotide variants (SNVs), copy number losses, gene fusions and splicing
105 alterations (14, 15). Commonly inactivated tumour suppressor genes include
106 cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (*CDKN2A*), BRCA1 associated protein 1
107 (*BAP1*) and neurofibromin 2 (*NF2*), large tumour suppressor kinase 2 (*LATS2*)
108 and SET Domain Containing 2 (*SETD2*). MPM is characterised by chromosomal
109 instability and extensive somatic copy number alterations with recurrent allelic
110 losses in regions such as 1p, 3p21, 6q, 9p21, 15q11-15 and 22q (16).

111 *CDKN2A* deletions are found in 56-70% of MPM and are associated with shorter
112 overall survival (17, 18). The *CDKN2A/ARF* locus (9p21) encodes for two cell
113 cycle regulatory proteins: p14ARF and p16INK4a, the latter being a negative

114 regulator of cyclin-dependent kinase 4/6 (CDK4/6) (19, 20). In a recent clinical
115 trial of personalised therapy in advanced NSCLC, *CDKN2A* loss was associated
116 with sensitivity to CDK4/6 inhibitors (19, 21). Considering the high frequency of
117 *CDKN2A* deletions in MPM and the fact that cell cycle deregulation is a hallmark
118 of this disease, we postulated that CDK4/6 inhibitors might constitute a novel
119 therapeutic approach in MPM. In the last decade, several selective CDK4/6
120 inhibitors, abemaciclib, ribociclib and palbociclib, have been approved for the
121 treatment of metastatic breast cancer (22-24).

122 In the present work, we investigated the efficacy of CDK4/6 inhibitors in preclinical
123 models of MPM to investigate their potential in the treatment of MPM. We also
124 assessed the prognostic impact of *CDK4* or *CDK6* overexpression in primary
125 tumours in patients with MPM using publicly available transcriptomic data.

126

127 **Materials and methods**

128 **Cell culture and cell lines**

129 Five human MPM cell lines, including H28, H2452, H2052, MSTO-211H and
130 H226 were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC,
131 Manassas, Virginia). Three additional primary cell lines (ICO_MPM1, ICO_MPM2
132 and ICO_MPM3) were derived from pleural effusions obtained from three patients
133 with MPM. ICO_MPM1 and ICO_MPM3, were derived from two patients who
134 progressed to standard chemotherapy with platinum and pemetrexed, while
135 ICO_MPM2 was derived from a chemotherapy-naïve patient. Primary cells were
136 isolated and cultured as previously described (25). All cell lines were incubated
137 and maintained at 37°C in a humidified chamber containing 5% CO₂. All cells
138 were tested routinely (after defrosting or every four months) for mycoplasma
139 contamination by PCR. MSTO-211H and ICO_MPM3 cells were used for the in
140 vivo experiments because they were able to form tumours in athymic mice.

141 **Patient and tissue samples**

142 Patients with confirmed histological diagnosis of malignant pleural mesothelioma
143 were scheduled for routine surgery involving extended pleurectomy decortication
144 at the Glenfield Hospital (University of Leicester). Patients were approached 24
145 hours prior to their operation and provided with patient information regarding the
146 research. All patients signed informed consent prior to surgery. Seventy-nine
147 patient MPM samples were obtained at the time of surgery. Following surgery, all
148 patients were longitudinally tracked until disease progression with CT monitoring,
149 and monitored for survival.

150

151 **Oncoscan Analysis**

152 DNA was extracted with the GeneRead DNA FFPE kit (Qiagen, Manchester, UK).
153 Eighty nanograms of genomic DNA were analysed using the OncoScan FFPE
154 Assay Kit (Affymetrix, Wooburn Green High Wycombe, UK). The BioDiscovery
155 Nexus Express 10.0 for OncoScan software was used to determine copy number
156 alterations and loss of heterozygosity (LOH).

157 **Antibodies and drugs**

158 Antibodies against total Rb (#9313), p-Rb (#8180), CDK4 (#12790), CDK6
159 (#13331), cyclin D1 (#2922), p16 (#80772) and β -actin (#4970) were purchased
160 from Cell Signaling Technology (Danvers, Massachusetts) and were used
161 following manufacturer instructions for western blot.

162 Abemaciclib (LY2835219) was purchased from Selleckchem (Houston, Texas).
163 Palbociclib (PD0332991) was provided by Pfizer, Inc (San Diego, California).
164 Cisplatin, pemetrexed and gemcitabine were obtained at the Catalan Institute of
165 Oncology pharmacy.

166 ***In vitro* and *in vivo* drug experiments**

167 For *in vitro* experiments, cell lines were plated into 6-well plates and treated with
168 abemaciclib or palbociclib with 0 (control), 10, 100, 250 or 500 nM for 1, 3 or 15
169 days. Doses below micromolar range would be clinically well tolerated. For *in vivo*
170 assays, mice were randomly treated with i) vehicle, 200 μ l of 0.05 N sodium
171 lactate pH 4.0 by oral gavage five days a week; ii) cisplatin alone, 3.5 mg/kg

172 administered intraperitoneally once a week or combined with pemetrexed, 100
173 mg/kg administered intraperitoneally twice a week; iii) gemcitabine, 75 mg/kg
174 administered intraperitoneally twice a week; iv) abemaciclib, 150 mg/kg by oral
175 gavage five days over seven days or v) palbociclib, 150 mg/kg by oral gavage
176 five days over seven days. Mice with subcutaneous tumours were treated during
177 twenty-six days, while mice harbouring orthotopic lung derived MSTO-211H and
178 ICO_MPM3 xenografts were treated during forty days and fifty-two days,
179 respectively.

180 **Western blot analysis**

181 Total cell lysates and western blotting were performed as previously described
182 (26).

183 **Cell viability, cell cycle and apoptosis analysis**

184 Cell viability was evaluated by cell counting and colony formation assays as
185 described elsewhere (27). For colony formation tests cells were grown for 15 days
186 and medium was renewed every 4 days. Cell cycle and apoptosis were analysed
187 by flow cytometry and propidium iodide incorporation as described in (28). A
188 minimum of 1×10^4 cells were analysed per determination. All experiments were
189 repeated at least three times with similar results: cell counting assay comprised
190 3 measurements in 3 biological replicates; cell cycle comprised 3 biological
191 replicates; and apoptosis comprised multiple biological replicates 10 for MSTO-
192 211H, 4 for H28 and 3 for ICO_MPM3. P-values were adjusted using FDR.

193 **Measurement of cellular senescence**

194 The evaluation of senescence-associated β -Galactosidase (SA- β -Gal)
195 expression was performed as previously described (29). Experiments included 3
196 measurements in at least 3 biological replicates.

197 ***In vivo* MPM subcutaneous preclinical drug assays in nude mice**

198 To investigate the efficacy of palbociclib in the treatment of MPM, we used the
199 MSTO-211H cell line, derived from a patient who had not received prior
200 chemotherapy and able to grow in athymic mice. For subcutaneous xenograft

201 development, 4×10^6 MSTO-211H cells growing exponentially were suspended
202 in 300 μ l PBS and subcutaneously inoculated into the right flanks of 23 six-week-
203 old male athymic nude (Hsd:Athymic Nude-Foxn1^{nu}) mice (Envigo, Indiana,
204 Indianapolis). Once the tumours reached a homogeneous average volume size
205 of 300–400 mm³ as including criteria, mice (n=21) were randomly assigned into
206 three groups (n=7 per group) and treated with i) vehicle; ii) cisplatin combined
207 with pemetrexed or iii) palbociclib as described above. To evaluate efficacy,
208 tumour volumes ($V = \pi/6 \times L \times W^2$) were measured twice per week with callipers
209 and the weight of each animal was measured every day. After 26 days of
210 treatment, mice were euthanised by cervical dislocation and the tumours were
211 excised, weighted and processed for histologic and RNA studies following
212 standard protocols. The mean volume + SD were calculated using R software
213 v.3.5.0 (30). Daily differences among treatments were analysed using Kruskal-
214 Wallis tests, with FDR adjustment.

215 ***In vivo* MPM orthotopic preclinical drug assays in tumours nude mice**

216 To investigate the efficacy of CDK4/6 inhibitors in tumours after progression to
217 standard first-line chemotherapy, we generated two different chemoresistant
218 MPM orthotopic models by implanting i) MSTO-211H subcutaneous xenografted
219 tumours treated with cisplatin plus pemetrexed from the previous experiments or
220 ii) chemoresistant patient-derived subcutaneous xenografted tumours in the
221 thoracic cavity of six-week-old male athymic nude mice following our previously
222 reported procedures (31). As we described, mice were anaesthetised with a
223 continuous flow of 1% to 3% isoflurane/oxygen mixture (2 L/min) and subjected
224 to right thoracotomy. Mice were situated in left lateral decubitus position, and a
225 small transverse skin incision (5–8 mm) was made in the right chest wall. Chest
226 muscles were separated by a sharp dissection and costal and intercostal muscles
227 were exposed. An intercostal incision of 2 to 4 mm on the third or fourth rib on
228 the chest wall was made and a small tumour piece of 2 to 4 mm³ was introduced
229 into the chest cavity and the tumour specimens were anchored to the lung surface
230 with Prolene 7.0 suture. Next, the chest wall incision was closed with surgery
231 staples, and finally chest muscles and skin were closed. The waiting time
232 between tumour implantation and the beginning of treatments was of 2 weeks

233 based on our previous orthotopic xenograft MPM models experience. For the
234 orthotopic xenograft model, thirty-three mice were randomised into three groups
235 (n=11 per group) and treated with i) vehicle; ii) cisplatin alone or iii) palbociclib as
236 previously mentioned for forty days. For the patient-derived orthotopic xenograft
237 model, thirty-one mice were randomised into four groups (n=7-8 per group) and
238 treated with i) vehicle; ii) gemcitabine; iii) abemaciclib or iv) palbociclib as
239 previously described for fifty-two days. In both orthotopic experiments, mice were
240 weighed daily and monitored for the presence of breathing problems. After
241 stopping treatments, all live mice remained untreated until human endpoint
242 (defined as presenting respiratory problems or excessive body weight loss).
243 Orthotopic tumours were collected from euthanised mice and processed for
244 histological studies. Survival curves for each cohort of mice were calculated using
245 the Kaplan-Meier method and the differences between groups were compared
246 using Cox proportional hazards model.

247 **Immunohistochemistry studies**

248 Paraffin sections of subcutaneous MSTO-211H xenografted tumours harvested
249 when the mice were euthanised 26 days post-treatment were used to assess
250 macrophages and NK cells infiltration by immunohistochemistry. Antibodies used
251 were anti-F4/80 (#70076 from Cell Signalling Technologies) as macrophage
252 marker and recombinant anti-NCR1 (ab233558 from Abcam, Cambridge, UK) as
253 NK cell marker. All slides were coded and examined in blinded manner.

254 ***In silico* analysis of publicly available RNA-sequencing data**

255 Public data from RNA-seq cohorts published by Bueno et al. (14, 15) and The
256 Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA-MESO) (15) were used to assess differences in
257 survival. Gene expression ($\log_2(\text{TPM})$) was stratified using the median, and Cox
258 proportional-hazards models adjusted for sex, stage, age and histology were
259 fitted to assess differences in survival using R software (30).

260 **Whole Exome Sequencing (WES) and RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) analysis** 261 **of patient-derived cell lines**

262 Paired-end RNA sequencing was performed on an Illumina HiSeq 2500, with 100
263 bp long reads. Genomic DNA and total RNA were submitted to the Centro
264 Nacional de Análisis Genómico (CNAG, Barcelona, Spain), for WES and RNA-
265 Seq library preparation and sequencing. All statistical analyses were done using
266 R software v.3.5.0 (30). Sequence data has been deposited at the European
267 Genome-phenome Archive (EGA), which is hosted by the EBI and the CRG,
268 under accession number EGAS00001005352.

269 **Statistics**

270 Cell proliferation assay was assessed using Wilcoxon signed rank tests
271 comparing each treatment with vehicle condition and adjusted using FDR
272 correction. Differences among treatment and vehicle conditions in the cell death
273 experiment were evaluated using Mann-Whitney U test for each comparison and
274 Kruskal-Wallis test if 3 conditions were simultaneously tested and adjusted
275 afterward using FDR. Cell cycle and senescence experiments were analysed
276 using proportion tests taking into consideration all the cells counted in the
277 abovementioned experiments. P-values were adjusted using FDR. For *in vivo*
278 experiments, the analysis of differences in body weight for orthotopic xenografts
279 was computed using a Mann-Whitney U test comparing the first and last day of
280 treatment in each treatment and adjusted with FDR. For subcutaneous
281 xenografts, a longitudinal analysis testing for differences in treatment slopes was
282 done using analysis of covariance. All tests were two-sided, and assumptions
283 were verified for all tests that required it. Homoscedasticity was also verified using
284 a Levene test. Regarding survival analysis, sample size was not calculated since
285 we used publicly available data Bueno et al. (14) and The Cancer Genome Atlas
286 (15). Cox proportional-hazards models adjusted for sex, stage, age, and histology
287 were fitted to assess the differences between gene expression (categorised using
288 the median log₂TPM value for each gene). For *in vivo* experiments, a Cox
289 proportional-hazards model was fitted to assess differences among
290 groups. Survival curves were plotted using Kaplan-Meier curves. P-value smaller
291 than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were
292 done using R software v.3.5.0 (30).

293 For additional information about methodology see supplementary material.

294 **Results**

295 **Genomic characterization of patient-derived MPM models and baseline** 296 **expression of genes involved in cell cycle in MPM cell lines**

297 Clinicopathological characteristics and main genomic alterations are shown in
298 **Table 1**. In all three patient-derived cell lines, *CDKN2A/p16* was deleted and *NF2*
299 was wild type, while *BAP1* was mutated in ICO_MPM1 (p.K651Yfs*1) and
300 ICO_MPM2 (p.R60X). Additional information about their mutational profile is
301 provided in **Supplementary Table S1**.

302 We examined by Western blot the expression levels of CDK4, CDK6, cyclin D1,
303 CDKN2A/p16 and RB proteins in 5 commercial and in 3 patient-derived MPM cell
304 lines (**Figure 1A**). p16 expression was not detected in any cell line, while all cell
305 lines showed some degree of cyclin D1 expression and retained RB expression.
306 CDK4 was expressed at relatively high level in most MPM cells, whereas CDK6
307 expression appeared to be comparatively lower. Additional information about
308 their mutational profile is provided in **Supplementary Table S2**.

309 **Antiproliferative effect of CDK4/6 inhibitors on human MPM cell lines**

310 All MPM cell lines treated with increasing concentrations of abemaciclib or
311 palbociclib for 72 hours, showed a decrease in cell number (**Figure 1B and**
312 **Supplementary Figure S1**). Treatment with abemaciclib and palbociclib at 100
313 or 500 nM significantly reduced cell number in comparison to control in all cell
314 lines tested ($p < 0.05$). At 10 nM, the cell number was significantly reduced in six
315 out of eight cell lines after treatment with abemaciclib ($p < 0.01$), while it was
316 significantly reduced in all cell lines after palbociclib treatment ($p < 0.05$).

317 The reduction in cell number after exposure to CDK4/6 inhibitors at 100 nM was
318 nearly 50% (mean $54.5\% \pm 5.5$ with abemaciclib and mean $53.4\% \pm 4.9$ with
319 palbociclib). At 500 nM, a reduction of 64.3% and 64.1% was observed with
320 abemaciclib and palbociclib respectively. MSTO-211H was the most sensitive cell
321 line to both CDK4/6 inhibitors at 100 nM and 500 nM doses. All primary cell lines

322 were sensitive to CDK4/6 inhibitors regardless of whether they had been derived
323 from a patient who was chemotherapy-naïve or who had received prior
324 chemotherapy. ICO_MPM2, which was derived from a chemotherapy-naïve
325 patient, was the most sensitive primary cell line to palbociclib with a cell number
326 reduction of $45.3\% \pm 5.2$ at 100 nM (**Figure 1B**). These antiproliferative effects
327 were confirmed by cell colony formation assay and crystal violet staining
328 (**Supplementary Figure S2A**). The ability to form colonies was completely
329 blocked when H226, H2052, ICO_MPM1 and ICO_MPM3 were treated with
330 abemaciclib and palbociclib at 250 and 500 nM (**Figure 1C**).

331 **Effect of CDK4/6 inhibitors on cell cycle in human MPM cell lines**

332 Three cell lines selected for expressing high levels of CDK4 and CDK6 proteins
333 (MSTO-211H, H28 and ICO_MPM3) were evaluated for alterations in cell cycle
334 progression after 24-hour treatment with 250 or 500 nM abemaciclib or
335 palbociclib. Compared with control, all cells treated with abemaciclib or
336 palbociclib at 500 nM were arrested at G1 phase ($p < 0.001$, **Figure 2A**). In
337 addition, a significant decrease in cell percentage in the G2/M phase ($p < 0.001$)
338 and in S phase ($p < 0.001$) was observed in the three cell lines after treatments at
339 250 nM and 500 nM compared to non-treated cells (**Supplementary Figure**
340 **S2B**). All changes in the percentage of cells in each phase of the cell cycle after
341 abemaciclib and palbociclib treatment are summarised in **Figure 2B**.

342

343 **Effect of CDK4/6 inhibitors on cell death and senescence in human MPM** 344 **cell lines**

345 As a next step, we investigated whether treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitors could
346 induce cell death in MPM cells. MSTO-211H, H28 and ICO_MPM3 cells were
347 treated with different concentrations of abemaciclib and palbociclib, as single
348 agents or in combination with the apoptosis inhibitor QVD for 72 hours and cell
349 death was quantified by FACS (**Supplementary Figure S3**). Neither inhibitor was
350 able to significantly increase the levels of apoptosis in MSTO-211H, H28 and
351 ICO_MPM3 cells at any of the doses tested. At the highest dose (500 nM), the

352 percentage of apoptotic cells reached 12% with abemaciclib and 8% with
353 palbociclib in MSTO-211H cells, 2% after abemaciclib and 3% after palbociclib in
354 H28 cells, and around 6% after either treatment in ICO_MPM3 cells.

355 To investigate whether CDK4/6 inhibitors promote senescence, both treated and
356 control MSTO-211H, H28 and ICO_MPM2 cells were stained using β -
357 galactosidase. A significant increase in the percentage of senescent cells was
358 detected in all cell lines treated with different concentrations of abemaciclib or
359 palbociclib ($p < 0.001$, **Figure 2C**). Specifically, the proportion of senescent SA- β -
360 gal positive MSTO-211H cells increased from 18% to 54% with 250 nM
361 abemaciclib and to 61% with 500 nM abemaciclib and to 52% with 250 nM
362 palbociclib and to 59% with 500 nM palbociclib. Likewise, an increase of
363 senescent cells was also observed in H28 cells treated with 250 nM or 500 nM of
364 either inhibitor. In ICO_MPM2 cells, the percentage of SA- β -gal positive cells
365 increased from 12% in control cells to 41% after abemaciclib and to 46% after
366 palbociclib treatments at 250 and 500 nM, respectively.

367 **Palbociclib reduced tumour growth and improved overall survival in mice** 368 **bearing MPM tumours**

369 The effect of palbociclib *in vivo* was examined by implanting subcutaneously
370 MSTO-211H cells into the right flanks of athymic mice. After 26 days of treatment,
371 the mean volume of tumours implanted subcutaneously in vehicle-treated mice
372 was $1816 \pm 795.2 \text{ mm}^3$; in cisplatin plus pemetrexed-treated mice was $1647.1 \pm$
373 733.8 mm^3 whereas for palbociclib-treated mice it was $524.2 \pm 236.6 \text{ mm}^3$ (**Figure**
374 **3A and Supplementary Figure S4A**). Differences among palbociclib and the two
375 other cohorts were already statistically significant at day 16 ($p = 0.043$, **Figure 3B**).
376 At mice sacrifice, 26 days post-treatment, a significant decrease in the tumour
377 weight was observed for palbociclib-treated mice respect to vehicle and
378 combined chemotherapy-treated mice (0.35 vs 1.1 and 1.13 gr; $p = 0.01$ and
379 $p = 0.007$, respectively, **Figure 3C and 3D**). No differences were observed at
380 histological level (**Supplementary Figure S5**). The body weight of the mice was
381 monitored to evaluate the potential side effects of treatments (**Figure 3E**). In
382 those mice treated with palbociclib, no body weight loss was observed during the

383 experiment, suggesting that palbociclib did not exert significant systemic toxicity
384 at the doses used in this study. After 26 days of treatment, we quantified the
385 macrophages and NK cells infiltration into the subcutaneous MPM tumours
386 xenografts (**Figure 3F**). A statistically significant increase in the tumour
387 associated macrophages (F4/80⁺ cells) was observed for palbociclib-treated
388 tumours respect to vehicle and combined chemotherapy-treated tumours (0.09
389 vs 0.048 and 0.048; p=0.041, respectively, **Figure 3G**). No significant differences
390 in the percentage of tumour infiltrated NK cells (NCR1⁺ cells) were found between
391 vehicle, cisplatin plus pemetrexed and palbociclib-treated tumours (0.04 vs 0.004
392 and 0.10; p=0.58, respectively, **Figure 3J**).

393 To preclinically investigate the efficacy of palbociclib as second-line treatment in
394 MPM tumours refractory to conventional chemotherapy, we re-implanted
395 orthotopically in the thoracic space small fragments from one of the subcutaneous
396 tumours derived from MSTO-211H cells previously treated with cisplatin plus
397 pemetrexed. After 40 days of treatment, no vehicle-treated mice were alive (0/11;
398 0%); only three platinum-treated mice were alive (3/11; 27.3%), while seven
399 palbociclib-treated mice were still alive (7/11; 63.6%) (**Figure 4A**). Animals
400 (93.9%) were sacrificed due to dyspnoea or excessive weight loss (31/33).
401 Overall survival analysis showed a significant reduction in the risk of death for
402 palbociclib-treated mice compared with vehicle (HR=0.04 [95% CI 0.01-0.17]) or
403 with cisplatin (HR=0.11 [95% CI 0.03-0.41]).

404 Those mice that were alive after 40 days of treatment (n=10) were maintained
405 without treatment and followed up until endpoint. After six days of stopping
406 treatments, all the remaining platinum-treated mice (n=3) were dead, whereas
407 two out of seven palbociclib-treated mice were still alive after two months without
408 receiving any treatment. Palbociclib treatment did not exert any substantial
409 change in body weight between the first and the last day of treatment
410 (**Supplementary Figure S4B**). Representative pictures of MSTO-211H
411 orthotopic tumours from each group of treatment are shown in **Figure 4B** and
412 **Supplementary Figure S6**. Histopathological analysis of the MPM tumour
413 xenografts grown orthotopically in mice accurately reproduced the natural history
414 of mesothelioma (**Figure 4C** and **Supplementary Figure S7**).

415 Next, we generated an additional orthotopic model by implanting into the pleural
416 space of nude mice small tumour fragments harvested from a xenograft
417 generated by injecting subcutaneously the patient derived cell-line ICO_MPM3.
418 Orthotopically implanted mice (n=31) were allocated in the different treatment
419 groups and treatment was started 15 days after implantation, and mice were
420 treated continuously for 52 days. Then, mice were maintained alive without
421 treatment and followed up until human endpoint. (**Figure 4D**). Overall survival
422 analysis shows a significant reduction in the risk of death for palbociclib-treated
423 mice compared with vehicle group (HR=0.23 [95% CI 0.06-0.85]; p=0.027). No
424 significant differences were observed in the risk of death for gemcitabine-treated
425 mice (HR=0.50 [95% CI 0.17-1.40]; p=0.19) and abemaciclib-treated mice
426 (HR=0.42 [95% CI 0.14-1.23]; p=0.12) compared to vehicle. Representative
427 images of orthotopic tumours from each treatment group are shown in **Figure 4E-**
428 **F**.

429 **Gene-expression profiling in cell lines and xenografts treated with CDK4/6** 430 **inhibitors**

431 To determine the functional consequences of CDK4/6 inhibitor treatment, we
432 performed transcriptomic analysis of MSTO-211H cells treated with abemaciclib
433 or palbociclib at 250 nM for 72 hours. In addition, tumour xenografts treated with
434 palbociclib were also evaluated. After treatment with either CDK4/6 inhibitor, a
435 significant downregulation in the expression levels was observed in the MSTO-
436 211H cell line for genes related with cell cycle, such as regulation of transcription
437 genes involved in G1-S transition of mitotic cell cycle, nucleus organization and
438 mitotic spindle assembly and organization (**Supplementary Figure S8 and**
439 **Supplementary Table S3**). On the other hand, there was a significant
440 upregulation of genes related to interferon signalling pathways, lymphocyte
441 migration and chemotaxis, complement activation and antigen presentation
442 pathways, such as MHC protein complex. Furthermore, the transcriptomic
443 analysis of palbociclib-treated tumours in xenografted mice showed similar
444 results (**Supplementary Figure S9**).

445 **CDK4 and CDK6 overexpression are associated with poor prognosis in** 446 **patients with MPM**

447 Based on these results, we evaluated the prognostic value of *CDK4* and *CDK6*
448 overexpression using publicly available transcriptomic data from two cohorts of
449 MPM patients. Patients with *CDK4* overexpression (i.e., above the median) had
450 significantly shorter overall survival in both cohorts (12.6 and 13.3 months,
451 respectively) compared with patients with lower expression (23.5 and 25.9
452 months respectively). *CDK4* overexpression remained statistically significant
453 after adjusting by age, gender, tumour stage and histologic subtype in each
454 dataset, as well as in the combined analysis of both series (HR=2.10 [95% CI
455 1.53–2.88]; p=4.2e-06; **Figure 5A**). Patients with *CDK6* overexpression (i.e.,
456 above the median) had significantly shorter overall survival (12.6 months)
457 compared with patients with lower expression (20.3 months; p=0.00026) in the
458 Bueno cohort and there was a trend toward shorter overall survival in the TCGA
459 dataset (15 versus 23.6 months; p=0.060). Nevertheless, *CDK6* overexpression
460 remained statistically significant in the combined analysis after adjusting by age,
461 gender, tumour stage and histologic subtype in the Bueno cohort, and also in the
462 combined cohort (HR=1.74 [95% CI 1.32–2.29]; p=5.4e-05; **Figure 5B**).

463 As previously reported (9,10), low expression of *CDKN2A* was associated with
464 shorter overall survival in both cohorts and was independently associated with
465 worse prognosis in the combined cohort including Bueno and TCGA (HR=0.49
466 [95% CI 0.36–0.66]; p=3.4e-06; **Supplementary Figure S10A**). In the TCGA
467 cohort, only two tumours harboured an *RB1* homologous deletion,
468 while *CDKN2A/p16* deletion was a common event present in 34 out of 74 cases
469 (46%).

470 *CDKN2A* copy number was assessed in an independent cohort of 79 MPM
471 acquired at radical surgery involving extended pleurectomy decortication. Patient
472 clinicopathological characteristics are outlined in **Supplementary Table S4**.
473 Homozygous loss of 9p21.3 encompassing *CDKN2A* was observed in 40
474 samples (50.6%), while copy number loss/LOH was observed in 18 (22.7%).
475 *CDKN2A* homozygous loss was associated with shorter median overall survival
476 (10.98 months) compared to euploid *CDKN2A* (45.8 months; HR=0.37 [95% CI
477 0.22 - 0.62]; p=0.0002; **Supplementary Figure S10B**). *CDKN2A* copy number
478 loss/LOH was associated with shorter median overall survival (8.52 months)

479 compared to wild-type *CDKN2A* (45.8 months; HR=0.18 [95% CI 0.08-0.40];
480 p=0.0001). There were no statistically significant differences in overall survival
481 among patients harbouring *CDKN2A* homozygous deletion compared to those
482 with *CDKN2A* copy number loss/LOH (HR=0.89 [95% CI 0.49-1.59]; p=0.158).

483

484 **Discussion**

485 MPM is a rapidly fatal neoplastic disease in which therapeutic options are limited.
486 We investigated the role of CDK4/6 inhibition in MPM because cell cycle
487 deregulation is a relevant hallmark in this disease and *CDKN2A/p16* deletion is a
488 common genomic event associated to worse clinical outcome in MPM (17, 18).

489 The efficacy of palbociclib has been previously studied in *in vitro* models of MPM
490 (29). However, the antitumour activity of CDK4/6 inhibitors has not yet been
491 evaluated using primary patient-derived cell models of MPM neither *in vivo*
492 models of MPM. In our work, we assessed the efficacy of two CDK4/6 inhibitors,
493 abemaciclib and palbociclib, in a subset of five commercial and three primary
494 patient-derived cell culture models obtained from pleural effusions of patients with
495 MPM (one chemotherapy-naïve and two after progression to standard first-line
496 chemotherapy). Furthermore, we performed not only *in vivo* basic subcutaneous
497 drug response studies in xenografts derived from one chemotherapy-naïve MPM
498 cell line, but also advanced studies by means of orthotopic implanted xenografts
499 from a cell line-derived tumour previously treated with cisplatin plus pemetrexed
500 and from a chemoresistant primary cell line-derived tumour. Remarkably all the
501 cell lines were sensitive to palbociclib and to abemaciclib. Treatment with
502 abemaciclib or palbociclib significantly reduced cell proliferation, as evaluated by
503 cell number counting or by colony formation ability, in all the cell lines including
504 in the primary ones derived from pleural liquid from patients resistant to
505 chemotherapy. *In vitro* experiments underscore two important points: i) no
506 substantial differences were found in the antiproliferative effect of both inhibitors;
507 and ii) the sensitivity to CDK4/6 inhibitors was not correlated with the endogenous
508 expression levels of CDK4 or CDK6. We consider that there is still an unmet need
509 of biomarkers able to predict clinical benefit to CDK4/6 inhibitors. In our work, we

510 confirmed that *CDKN2A/p16* deletion is associated with shorter overall survival
511 in a cohort of MPM patients with resectable disease. These results are consistent
512 with previous publications where *CDKN2A/p16* loss predicted worse clinical
513 outcome in patients with resected and advanced epithelioid MPM (18).

514 By analysing publicly available transcriptomic data of MPM, we found that
515 overexpression of CDK4 or CDK6 is also associated with shorter overall survival.
516 Together these findings suggest that cell cycle deregulation may confer an
517 aggressive biological behaviour in mesothelioma and reinforce our hypothesis
518 about further investigating CDK4/6 inhibitors in MPM patients.

519 We investigated the impact of abemaciclib and palbociclib treatment on cell cycle
520 progression, cellular senescence and apoptosis induction. These experiments
521 were performed using three cell lines that were sensitive to both drugs, including
522 a primary cell line derived from a patient resistant to chemotherapy. As expected,
523 the treatment with abemaciclib and palbociclib caused cell cycle arrest at G1
524 phase but also promoted cellular senescence. However, neither abemaciclib nor
525 palbociclib activated programmed cell death or apoptosis as indicated by
526 negligible subG1 accumulation or propidium iodide incorporation. The observed
527 increase on cellular senescence induced by both drugs could be linked to
528 apoptosis resistance mechanisms (23, 32). As proposed by other groups (29, 33,
529 34), our results reinforce the cytostatic mechanism of action of CDK4/6 inhibitors
530 and underscore that these should be given sequentially after completing
531 chemotherapy treatment (35). However, the low cell death observed *in vitro* does
532 not eliminate the possibility that palbociclib, by inducing senescence in a few
533 cells, may promote *in vivo* cytotoxicity mediated by Natural Killer cells. This
534 phenomenon has been described in lung cancer, in which Natural Killers
535 participate in tumour reduction upon treatment with MEK inhibitors and
536 palbociclib (36, 37).

537 To explore potential activation of compensatory pathways, we performed gene
538 set enrichment analysis of the transcriptome of MSTO-211H cells treated with
539 abemaciclib or palbociclib *in vitro* or subcutaneously implanted in mice. This
540 experiment showed downregulation of genes involved in G1-S transition of mitotic
541 cell cycle, nucleus organization and mitotic spindle assembly and organization.

542 In concordance with studies conducted in other tumour types, genes encoding
543 interferon signalling and antigen presentation pathways were upregulated after
544 CDK4/6 pharmacological inhibition (34). In melanoma, CDK4/6 inhibition
545 activates p53 by lowering PRMT5 which leads to altered MDM4 splicing and
546 significantly reduced protein expression (38, 39). Other studies performed in
547 breast cancer cell lines and transgenic mice models have shown that abemaciclib
548 treatment increased the expression of antigen processing and presentation and
549 even suppressed the proliferation of regulatory T cells (24, 34). In the present
550 study, we have observed that palbociclib treatment increase the number of
551 tumour associated macrophages in subcutaneous MPM tumour xenografts and
552 there was a trend toward higher NK cell infiltration, but further studies evaluating
553 the functional consequences of the treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitors on the
554 tumour immune contexture are warranted in mesothelioma.

555 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that effectiveness of
556 abemaciclib and palbociclib were evaluated using preclinical *in vivo*
557 subcutaneous and orthotopic MPM tumour models. Among the available cell line
558 models, MSTO-211H cell line was selected for the *in vivo* subcutaneous and
559 orthotopic experiments because i) it expresses CDK4 and CDK6; ii) it is the most
560 sensitive cell line to palbociclib at 500 nM; and iii) it was tumorigenic in athymic
561 mice. Our results showed that palbociclib reduced tumour size in a subcutaneous
562 mouse model of chemo-naïve MSTO-211H cells compared with standard
563 chemotherapy (cisplatin plus pemetrexed). An increased expression of anti-
564 apoptotic proteins after long-term chemotherapy treatment could explain the
565 chemoresistance in this model (40). We tried to replicate a situation representing
566 treatment after progression to platinum-based chemotherapy by generating an
567 orthotopic tumour mouse model and implanting in the pleura small solid
568 fragments of MSTO-211H xenografted tumours previously treated with
569 chemotherapy. In this advanced model of MPM, palbociclib significantly
570 increased the overall survival of mice compared with cisplatin-based
571 chemotherapy or vehicle; the benefits from treatment persisted even after
572 stopping the treatment. Our results reinforce the potential use of palbociclib as a
573 second-line treatment for patients with MPM that is resistant or has relapsed after

574 standard chemotherapy doublet treatment. Finally, we also use ICO_MPM3, a
575 patient-derived cell line also tumorigenic in athymic mice to test the efficacy of
576 CDK4/6 inhibitors *in vivo*.

577 Some limitations of our study are the absence of a wide range of available
578 commercial MPM cell lines and the need for preclinical *in vivo* models
579 representing the heterogeneity of the disease, including the adaptive immune
580 system. However, in our study we have combined commercial, primary patient-
581 derived lines as well as orthotopic models where mesothelioma grows in its
582 corresponding microenvironment and can recapitulate the disease behaviour.

583 A phase II clinical study of abemaciclib in patients harbouring p16ink4a deficient,
584 relapsed MPM has recently completed accrual (NCT03654833). CDK4/6
585 inhibition in this cohort has been associated radiological responses however the
586 underlying molecular correlates of response are under investigation. Accordingly,
587 whole exome sequencing of the trial cohort is planned to uncover genomic
588 determinants of response.

589 In conclusion, our data support that treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitors, abemaciclib
590 or palbociclib, can reduce cell proliferation and induce cellular senescence in
591 MPM cell lines and palbociclib can increase overall survival of mice with
592 orthotopically implanted MPM cells. A remarkable and sustained response to
593 palbociclib was observed in xenografts of MPM tumour resistant to cisplatin and
594 pemetrexed which was then implanted orthotopically in the pleural space of mice.
595 Transcriptomic analysis of cell lines and xenografted tumours treated with
596 CDK4/6 inhibitors showed an increased expression of interferon signalling
597 pathway and antigen presenting processes, suggesting that CDK4/6 inhibitors
598 may favour potential response to immunotherapy. Our results warrant further
599 evaluation of CDK4/6 inhibitors as a second-line treatment in patients with
600 advanced MPM that has failed standard platinum-based chemotherapy.

601 Supplementary information is available at the British Journal of Cancer's website.

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747 **Figure legends**

748 **Figure 1. Quantification of the expression levels of key cell cycle regulators**
749 **and response to treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitors in a panel of commercial**
750 **MPM cell lines (MSTO-211H, H28, H226, H2052, H2452) and primary patient-**
751 **derived cultures (ICO_MPM1, ICO_MPM2, ICO_MPM3). (A)** Baseline protein
752 expression levels by Western blot of CDK4, CDK6, cyclin D1, Rb, phosphor-RB
753 and p16. **(B)** Number of viable cells was determined *in vitro* by cell counting in
754 the panel of cells after three days of treatment with increasing concentrations (0,
755 10, 100, 500 nM) of abemaciclib or palbociclib. Bar plots represent the means \pm
756 SD of 3 measurements in 3 biological replicates. Adjusted p-values were
757 calculated with Wilcoxon signed rank tests. In the graph, the p values are reported
758 with respected to 0 nM (*p < 0.05; **p < 0.01). **(C)** Colony formation assay
759 displaying treatment response to abemaciclib and palbociclib. A representative
760 image from 3 biological independent replicates is displayed.

761

762 **Figure 2. Effects of cell line treatments with CDK4/6 inhibitors abemaciclib**
763 **or palbociclib at 0, 250 or 500 nM doses to induce (A and B) cell-cycle arrest**
764 **and (C) senescence. (A)** MSTO-211H, H28 and ICO_MPM3 cells were
765 untreated and treated with both inhibitors for 24 hours and DNA content analysed
766 by flow cytometry. Cell cycle arrest at G1 phase was induced by both CDK4/6
767 inhibitors in the cell lines. **(B)** Percentage of cells in each phase of the cell cycle
768 phase in response to abemaciclib and palbociclib treatments at doses of 0, 250
769 or 500 nM for 24 hours. Cell cycle phase distribution analysis was done using
770 FlowJo software. Each value represents the mean \pm SD of 3 replicates. Adjusted
771 p values were considered significant when mean differed from control within each
772 phase of the cell cycle (*p < 0.05; ***p < 0.001). **(C)** A significant increase in the
773 number of SA- β -Gal positive cells was detected in MSTO-211H, H28 and
774 ICO_MPM2 treated. Data are expressed as a percentage of senescent cells
775 obtained from the mean value \pm SD of 3 replicates. Adjusted p-values < 0.05 were
776 considered significant.

777

778 **Figure 3. *In vivo* treatment with palbociclib in MSTO-211H subcutaneous**
779 **xenografted MPM model.** A xenografted subcutaneous tumour model was
780 established by inoculation of MSTO-211H cells into the flanks of athymic nude
781 mice (n=7 per group). Tumours' volume (A) was monitored by calliper measure
782 every four days (at each time point, a SD bar is shown). (B) Differences in tumour
783 volume for each day were represented using boxplots and compared using
784 Kruskal-Wallis test, adjusted by FDR and were significantly different at day 16. At
785 the end of the experiment, mice were sacrificed and (C and D) the tumours were
786 removed, weighted and photographed. Asterisks indicated absence of apparent
787 macroscopic tumour at sacrifice, while residual cells were identified by H&E
788 analysis. (E) Summary of the body weight values among first and last day of
789 treatment from all mice in *in vivo* subcutaneous tumour xenograft growth
790 experiment. Palbociclib did not exert any substantial change in the mice body
791 weight. Differences were evaluated by Mann-Whitney test and adjusted for FDR.
792 (F) Representative IHC images for (F.A) mouse macrophages that express F4/80
793 (brown staining) and (F.B) mouse NK cells that express NCR1 (brown staining)
794 infiltrated in the subcutaneous MPM tumours xenografted in athymic nude mice
795 after 26 days of treatment with vehicle, platinum plus pemetrexed or palbociclib.
796 Inset photos contains the digital whole slide image showing the infiltrated area of
797 tumour. Scale bar = 50 μ m. Dot plots showing (G) the mean F4/80⁺ intensity per
798 pixel (x-axis) or (J) the percentage of NCR1⁺ cells over total cells infiltrated in the
799 subcutaneous MPM tumour xenografted in athymic nude mice after 26 days of
800 treatment with vehicle, platinum plus pemetrexed or palbociclib (n= 5-7 per group).
801 Data are expressed as single data values (dots) + the mean. ANOVA test was
802 used to detect statistical differences between treatments (*p < 0.05).

803

804 **Figure 4. *In vivo* treatment with CDK4/6 inhibitors in advanced orthotopic**
805 **MPM models.** Two advanced orthotopic models were generated by implantation
806 in the lung of mice small solid fragments (2-3 mm³) of previously generated (A, B
807 and C) MSTO-211H subcutaneous cisplatin plus pemetrexed resistant tumour
808 xenograft or (D, E and F) chemoresistant patient-derived tumour xenograft. (A)
809 Kaplan-Meier curves showing survival of MSTO-211H orthotopic tumour-bearing
810 mice (n=33). (B) Representative MSTO-211H images of orthotopic tumours

811 dissected from each group of treatment and (C) histological characterization on
812 H&E sections (Scale bars = 100 μ m). (D) Kaplan-Meier curves showing survival
813 of ICO_MPM3 orthotopic tumour-bearing mice (n=29). (E) Representative
814 images of patient-derived orthotopic tumours dissected from each group of
815 treatment and (F) histological characterization on H&E sections (Scale bars = 100
816 μ m). Both orthotopic models accurately reproduce human MPM disease
817 characteristics as tumour grown from the site of implantation to all the pleural
818 space. Tumour mass area is delimited by white line.

819

820 **Figure 5. Kaplan-Meier plots of overall survival (OS) in MPM patients**
821 **according to (A) *CDK4* and (B) *CDK6* gene expression levels based on data**
822 **obtained from Bueno et al. (left column) and Hmeljak et al. (middle column)**
823 **cohorts or the combination of both (right column).** High levels of *CDK4* or
824 *CDK6* (red line) were significantly associated with poor OS in patients with MPM.
825 In each cohort, the high and low expression levels were defined based upon the
826 median. P-values and hazard ratios (HR) were calculated by likelihood ratio test
827 and multivariate Cox regression analysis respectively.

828

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835 **Authors' contributions**

836 **EA:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation,
837 Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing,
838 Visualization **AA:** Conceptualization, Software, Validation, Formal analysis,
839 Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing, Visualization **MMI:**
840 Methodology, Investigation, Resources, Data curation **MHM:** Methodology,
841 Validation, Investigation, Data Curation **DC:** Conceptualization, Software,

842 Validation, Formal analysis, Data Curation **MG**: Conceptualization, Resources,
843 Writing – Review & Editing **EP**: Resources, Writing – Review & Editing **MS**:
844 Resources, Writing – Review & Editing **SB**: Software, Validation, Data Curation
845 **AJS**: Resources, Writing – Review & Editing **AD**: Resources, Writing – Review
846 & Editing **RP**: Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing **SP**:
847 Resources, Writing – Review & Editing **SA**: Resources, Writing – Review &
848 Editing **IE**: Resources, Writing – Review & Editing **RR**: Resources, Writing –
849 Review & Editing **RL**: Resources, Validation, Data Curation **AV**: Resources,
850 Validation, Data Curation **ED**: Data Curation **MV**: Resources, Validation, Data
851 Curation **MSC**: Resources, Writing – Review & Editing **DF**: Resources,
852 Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Review &
853 Editing **CMP**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis,
854 Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing, Visualization **AV**:
855 Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data
856 Curation, Writing – Review & Editing, Visualization **XS**: Conceptualization,
857 Software, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing,
858 Visualization **EN**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis,
859 Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing –
860 Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding
861 acquisition.

862 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

863 The retrospective cohort was approved by a National Ethical Committee, under
864 the references 4/LO/1527 (a translational research platform entitled *Predicting*
865 *Drug and Radiation Sensitivity in Thoracic Cancers – also approved by University*
866 *Hospitals of Leicester NHS Trust under the reference IRAS131283*) and
867 14/EM/1159 (retrospective cohort). Pleural effusions samples were obtained after
868 patients signed the informed consent approved by the Hospital de Bellvitge
869 Ethical Committee (PR152/14). All the animal experiments were performed in
870 accordance with protocols approved by Animal Research Ethics Committee at
871 IDIBELL. This study was performed in accordance with the principles outlined in
872 the Declaration of Helsinki.

873 **Data availability**

874 All data generated or analysed during this study will be stored in EGA and
875 available on reasonable request.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 5

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Table 1. Clinicopathological characteristics and main genomic and protein alterations found in primary cell lines were derived from patients with pleural malignant mesothelioma. Additional predicted driver mutations have been identified using Cancer Genome Interpreter. (WES: whole exome sequencing; FISH: fluorescence in situ hybridization).

ID	Clinicopathological features					Molecular characterization by WES and FISH				
	Age	Sex	Asbestos exposure	Histology	Prior chemotherapy	<i>BAP1</i> (WES)	<i>TP53</i> (WES)	<i>NF2</i> (WES)	<i>CDKN2A</i> (FISH)	Additional predicted driver mutations
ICO_MPM1	77	M	No	Epithelioid	Yes	p.(Lys651_Lys661 del)	p.(Asn92Cys*26)	WT	Hemizygous deletion	<i>DHX15</i> p.(Pro478His) <i>SF3B1</i> p.(Tyr623Cys)
ICO_MPM2	73	F	Yes	Epithelioid	No	p.(Arg60*)	WT	WT	Hemizygous deletion	<i>CSNK2A1</i> p.(Asp210Tyr)
ICO_MPM3	70	M	No	Epithelioid	Yes	WT	WT	WT	Homozygous deletion	<i>ACO1</i> p.(Arg802His) <i>ABL1</i> p.(Gly1060Asp) <i>INPP4A</i> p.(Arg244Trp) <i>EP300</i> p.(Arg1356*) <i>SPEN</i> p.(Ser260Ile) <i>CREBBP</i> p.(Trp1718*)